

Meta-analysis of 20,533 human metagenomes defines an index of oral to gut microbial introgression and associations with age, sex, BMI, and diseases

Paolo Manghi¹, Lucas Schiffer^{2,3}, Davide Golzato¹, Jennifer Wokaty⁴, Francesco Beghini¹, Chloe Mirzayi⁴, Sehyun Oh⁴, Samuel David Gamboa-Tuz⁴, Arianna Bonetti¹, Giacomo D'Amato¹, Rimsha Azhar⁴, Gianmarco Piccinno¹, Kelly Eckenrode⁴, Fatima Zohra⁴, Valentina Giunchiglia¹, Marisa Metzger¹, Anna Pedrotti¹, Ilya Likhokin⁵, Shaimaa Elsafoury⁴, Ludwig Geistlinger⁴, Aitor Blanco-Miguez¹, Andrew Maltez Thomas¹, Moreno Zolfo¹, Marcel Ramos⁴, Mireia Valles-Colomer¹, Sabrina Tamburini⁶, Francesco Asnicar¹, Heidi Jones⁴, Curtis Huttenhower^{7,8}, Vincent Carey⁹, Sean Davis¹², Edoardo Pasolli¹⁰, Nicola Segata^{1,11#*}, Levi Waldron^{1,4#*}

Supplementary materials

1. Department CIBIO, University of Trento, Trento, Italy
2. Section of Computational Biomedicine, Boston University School of Medicine, Boston, MA, USA
3. Graduate Program in Bioinformatics, Boston University, Boston, MA, USA
4. Graduate School of Public Health and Health Policy and Institute for Implementation Science in Population Health, City University of New York, New York, New York, USA
5. Institute of Pharmacy and Molecular Biotechnology (IPMB), University of Heidelberg, Heidelberg, Germany
6. Harvard T.H. Chan School of Public Health, Boston, MA, USA
7. The Broad Institute of MIT and Harvard, Cambridge, MA, USA
8. Channing Division of Network Medicine, Brigham and Women's Hospital and Harvard Medical School, Boston, MA, USA
9. Department of Medicine, University of Colorado Anschutz, Aurora, CO, USA
10. Department of Agricultural Sciences, University of Naples, Naples, Italy
11. IEO, European Institute of Oncology, IRCCS, Milan, Italy

* equal contribution

to whom correspondence should be addressed

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Supplementary Tables

Supplementary Table 5.1. cMD 3: datasets, numbers, and publications.

Supplementary Table 5.2. Curated metadata for 20,533 samples and 90 cohorts.

Supplementary Table 5.3. Meta-analysis of sex-related microbial species/genera, pathways & KEGGs in 4,207 healthy adults (1,733 males and 2,474 females).

Supplementary Table 5.4. Meta-analysis of age-related microbial species/genera, pathways & KEGGs in 3,384 healthy adults.

Supplementary Table 5.5. Meta-analysis of BMI-related microbial species/genera, pathways & KEGGs in 4,977 healthy adults.

Supplementary Table 5.6. Meta-analysis of health- & disease-related microbial species & pathways in 3,462 adults (12 diseases, 1,619 cases, 1,843 controls).

Supplementary Table 5.7. 130 species of the oral cavity

Supplementary figures

Supplementary Figure 5.1. Meta-analysis of 4,207 individuals metagenomes from 15 datasets (2,474 females, 1,733 males) reveals sex-associated MetaCyc pathway differences in the healthy, adult, stool microbiome - a) 30 microbial MetaCyc pathways having the highest Standardized Mean Differences meta-analysis coefficient ($Q < 0.05$) of male vs. female samples. Effect-sizes are computed as Standardized Mean Differences from a linear model controlling for age, BMI, and sequencing depth on centered log-ratio transformed MetaCyc pathway relative abundances. Yellow-shape: significant effect-size ($Q < 0.2$). Light-blue: non significant effect-size. Black-diamonds: Standardized Mean Differences between all cases and controls synthesized by a meta-analysis. Boxplots span the interquartile range of the dataset-effects distribution. Yellow horizontal lines are the 95% confidence intervals of the meta-analysis effect-size.

Supplementary Figure 5.2. Meta-analysis of 4,207 individuals metagenomes from 15 datasets (2,474 females, 1,733 males) reveals sex-associated KEGG Orthologs differences in the healthy, adult, stool microbiome - a) 30 microbial KEGG-Orthologs having the highest Standardized Mean Differences meta-analysis coefficient ($Q < 0.05$) of male vs. female samples. Effect-sizes are computed as Standardized Mean Differences from a linear model controlling for age, BMI, and sequencing depth on centered log-ratio transformed KEGG Ortholog relative abundances. Yellow-shape: significant effect-size ($Q < 0.2$). Light-blue: non significant effect-size. Black-diamonds: Standardized Mean Differences between all cases and controls synthesized by a meta-analysis. Boxplots span the interquartile range of the dataset-effects distribution. Yellow horizontal lines are the 95% confidence intervals of the meta-analysis effect-size.

Supplementary Figure 5.3. Meta-correlation of age-related (N=3,385) MetaCyc pathways - a) 30 MetaCyc pathways having the highest meta-analysis correlation coefficient with subject age ($Q < 0.05$) with a prevalence of at least 10% in the cohort analyzed. Partial correlation are extracted by a linear model controlling for sex, BMI, and sequencing depth fit using centered log-ratio transformed MetaCyc pathway relative abundances. Yellow-shape: significant effect-size ($Q < 0.2$). Light-blue: non significant effect-size. Black-diamonds: meta-analysis correlation coefficient computed as a random-effect meta-analysis on Fisher-Z transformed correlation coefficient. Meta-analysis coefficients and confidence intervals are then reverted back with the inverse of the Fisher-Z transformation. Boxplots span the interquartile range of the single dataset-correlations distribution. Yellow horizontal lines represent the 95% confidence intervals of the meta-analysis correlation.

Supplementary Figure 5.4. Meta-correlation of BMI-related (N=4,978) MetaCyc pathways - a) 30 MetaCyc pathways having the highest meta-analysis correlation coefficient with subject age ($Q < 0.05$) with a prevalence of at least 10% in the cohort analyzed. Partial correlation are extracted by a linear model controlling for sex, age, and sequencing depth fit using centered log-ratio transformed MetaCyc pathway relative abundances. Yellow-shape: significant effect-size ($Q < 0.2$). Light-blue: non significant effect-size. Black-diamonds: meta-analysis correlation coefficient computed as a random-effect meta-analysis on Fisher-Z transformed correlation coefficient. Meta-analysis coefficients and confidence intervals are then reverted back with the inverse of the Fisher-Z transformation. Boxplots span the interquartile range of the single dataset-correlations distribution. Yellow horizontal lines represent the 95% confidence intervals of the meta-analysis correlation.

Supplementary Figure 5.5. Meta-correlation of age-related (N=3,385) KEGG Orthologs - a) 30 KEGG Orthologs having the highest meta-analysis correlation coefficient with subject age ($Q < 0.05$) with a prevalence of at least 10% in the cohort analyzed. Partial correlation are extracted by a linear model controlling for sex, BMI, and sequencing depth fit using centered log-ratio transformed KEGG Orthologs relative abundances. Yellow-shape: significant effect-size ($Q < 0.2$). Light-blue: non significant effect-size. Black-diamonds: meta-analysis correlation coefficient computed as a random-effect meta-analysis on Fisher-Z transformed correlation coefficient. Meta-analysis coefficients and confidence intervals are then reverted back with the inverse of the Fisher-Z transformation. Boxplots span the interquartile range of the single dataset-correlations distribution. Yellow horizontal lines represent the 95% confidence intervals of the meta-analysis correlation.

Supplementary Figure 5.6. Meta-correlation of BMI-related (N=4,978) KEGG Orthologs - a) 30 KEGG Orthologs having the highest meta-analysis correlation coefficient with subject age ($Q < 0.05$) with a prevalence of at least 10% in the cohort analyzed. Partial correlation are extracted by a linear model controlling for sex, age, and sequencing depth fit using centered log-ratio transformed KEGG Orthologs relative abundances. Yellow-shape: significant effect-size ($Q < 0.2$). Light-blue: non significant effect-size. Black-diamonds: meta-analysis correlation coefficient computed as a random-effect meta-analysis on Fisher-Z transformed correlation coefficient. Meta-analysis coefficients and confidence intervals are then reverted back with the inverse of the Fisher-Z transformation. Boxplots span the interquartile range of the single dataset-correlations distribution. Yellow horizontal lines represent the 95% confidence intervals of the meta-analysis correlation.

Supplementary Figure 5.7. Meta-analysis of 12 diseases and 25 cohorts reveal hallmarks of disease in the MetaCyc pathways of 1,843 matched controls and 1,619 diseased patients - a) 30 MetaCyc pathways having the highest Standardized Mean Differences meta-analysis coefficient ($Q < 0.05$) of diseased vs. control samples, with a prevalence of at least 10% in the cohort analyzed. Effect-sizes are computed as Standardized Mean Differences from a linear model controlling for sex, age, BMI, and sequencing depth on centered log-ratio transformed MetaCyc pathways relative-abundances. Effects of CRC, CD, UC, & T2D have been meta-analyzed in advance so these datasets do not dominate the rankings over the diseases for which a single dataset is available (ACVD, asthma, migraine, STH, cirrhosis, ME/CFS, schizophrenia, BD). Yellow shape: significant effect ($Q < 0.2$). Light-blue: non significant effect. Black diamonds: Standardized Mean Differences between all cases and controls synthesized by a meta-analysis. Boxplots span the interquartile range of the dataset-effects distribution. Yellow horizontal lines are the 95% confidence intervals of the random-effect.

Supplementary figure 5.8. Oral taxa Shannon-entropy in the human gut microbiome members is a potential indicator of disease - a) Boxplots showing the log-10 distributions of oral-cavity typical microbial species Shannon entropy in 10 cohorts of CRC patients (dark-yellow) and related controls (light-blue). Asterisk: Wilcoxon signed-rank test $P < 0.05$. AUCs the introgression score against CRC versus healthy conditions are presented. **b)** boxplots showing the log-10 distributions of oral-cavity typical microbial species Shannon entropy in 11 diseases (15 cohorts), divided by disease (orange) and controls (light-blue). Asterisk: Wilcoxon signed-rank test $P < 0.05$. AUCs the introgression score against disease versus healthy conditions are presented. **c)** Forest plot of the meta-analysis of association of disease or healthy conditions and oral species Shannon entropy in 25 cohorts. Single datasets effect sizes are computed as Standardized Mean Difference extracted by a linear model controlling for sex, age, and BMI fit using the oral Shannon entropy of the sample. Yellow: significant Wald-test ($P < 0.05$) of the beta of the condition. Grey: non significant beta-coefficient. Horizontal lines mark the 95% confidence intervals of the effects.